

Characterisation, Biofilm Formation and Antifungal Susceptibility Pattern of *Candida* Species in Cancer Patients at Kidwai Memorial Institute of Oncology, Bengaluru

Joseph J¹, Sumathi B G², Sinha M³, Vardhana H⁴, Shetty N S⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Department of Microbiology, Kidwai Memorial Institute of Oncology, Bengaluru, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Joseph J

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Abstract:

Background: Biofilm formation is seen in many pathogens like bacteria, fungi etc. It is one of the virulence factors of *Candida* species, an important pathogen and commensal. Indiscriminate use of antifungal agents, especially azole group in cancer patients may contribute to emergence of resistance in *Candida* isolates. Biofilm producing property of *Candida* also contributes to non-response to antifungals. Hence, speciation and detection of biofilm is useful for clinical management of *Candida* infections in cancer patients. Aims of this prospective study was to detect biofilm formation and antifungal susceptibility to *Candida* species isolated from different clinical samples in cancer patients.

Methods: A total of 40 clinically significant isolates of *Candida* species from various clinical samples were characterised with Gram's stain, germ tube test, carbohydrate fermentation test, chromogenic media and micro morphology on cornmeal agar. Biofilm formation was detected by three standard methods-Tissue culture plate method, Tube method and Congo red agar method. Antifungal susceptibility testing was performed manually with two antifungal agents of the azole group (fluconazole-25µg, voriconazole-1µg).

Results: Out of 40 *Candida* isolates, 13 were *Candida albicans* and 27 were nonalbicans *Candida* (*C.tropicalis*-14, *C.parapsilosis*-5, *C.glabrata*-3, *C.krusei*-2, *C.guilliermondii*-2, and *C.lusitaniae*- 1). Biofilm production was seen in 31 *Candida* species (8 *C.albicans* and 23 nonalbicans *Candida*). Antifungal susceptibility was performed for all isolates of which 12 were fluconazole resistant and 3 were voriconazole resistant.

Conclusion: *C.tropicalis* (35%) was the most common *Candida* species isolated from cancer patients. Biofilm formation was seen in 78% of *Candida* species (*C.albicans* -26% and nonalbicans *Candida*-74%). Thirty percent *Candida* isolates were fluconazole resistant and 8% were voriconazole resistant. Considering high prevalence of nonalbicans *Candida* species and species-specific intrinsic resistance to antifungals in few of them, it is important to speciate *Candida* isolates causing infections in cancer patients along with their biofilm formation and antifungal susceptibilities.

Keywords: *Candida albicans*; non-albicans *Candida*; Cancer; Biofilm.

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Introduction

Candidiasis is the commonest fungal disease causing superficial, subcutaneous, and systemic and opportunistic infections in humans [1]. The number of non-albicans *Candida* species has expanded dramatically over the past 20 years, despite *C. albicans* being the most common species. Because of the shift, there is a decreased susceptibility to antifungals and a high mortality rate.

This requires prompt and accurate species identification, which improves our understanding of the risk factors, clinical traits, and outcomes associated with these pathogens to help clinicians choose the best treatment [2]. Cancer patients being immunosuppressed are vulnerable to infections. Since candidiasis is the most common disseminated fungal infection in cancer patients, an early

diagnosis of candidiasis is of great importance for patient management, as it leads to the selection of a species-specific antifungal therapy rapidly [3]. Biofilm formation is one of the virulence factors of *Candida* species. Early detection of biofilm production is useful for clinical management of *Candida* infections in cancer patients. Availability of key nutrients, chemotaxis towards surface, surface adhesins and presence of surfactants are some factors which influence biofilm formation.

Microorganisms growing in a biofilm are intrinsically more resistant to antimicrobial agents than planktonic cells [4]. Indiscriminate use of antifungal drugs, especially azole group in cancer patients may contribute to emergence of resistance in *Candida* isolates. [5]. Knowledge of the changing

epidemiology of infections has a pivotal role in its management. This study was undertaken to detect biofilm formation and antifungal susceptibility of *Candida* species isolated from different clinical samples in cancer patients by various phenotypic methods.

Materials and Methods

A prospective study was done in department of microbiology, Kidwai Memorial Institute of Oncology, a tertiary care cancer hospital for the period of 6 months (June 2023 – November 2023) after getting ethical clearance from hospital ethical committee. A total of 40 clinically significant isolates of *Candida* species from various clinical samples received in microbiology department were the source for the study.

The various clinical samples included blood, pus, urine, vaginal swab, ear swab, bronchoalveolar lavage, oral swab, sputum, urine etc. Patient demographic details such as age, sex, and clinical information were collected. The *Candida* isolates selected for our study included cancer patients in whom no other aerobic pathogen was identified and *Candida* infections were associated with clinical signs and symptoms. But repeat culture and isolation of *Candida* could not be performed for confirmation. Samples were first subjected to gram's stain, where they appeared as gram positive budding yeast cells. Presence of few to many pus cells was mandatory to consider infection.

However in patients with febrile neutropenia or pancytopenia, even absence of pus cells was considered as probable infection. In stool samples, pseudohyphae formation was checked in wet mount which is an indication of active infection. Samples were inoculated on Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA) which showed cream colored, smooth and pasty colonies. Colonies on SDA were again subjected to gram's stain for confirmation. Blood samples were directly inoculated into BacT/Alert blood culture bottles and gram's stain was done after bottle flagging positive. 40 *Candida* isolates which showed moderate to heavy growth in SDA were further speciated by conventional phenotypic methods such as:

Germ tube test: This test was used to differentiate *Candida albicans* and non-*albicans candida*. An isolated colony of *Candida* was suspended in a test tube containing 0.5 ml of human plasma or serum [6]. After incubation at 35-37°C for 2-3 hours, a drop of suspension placed on a glass slide was examined under low power and high-power objectives of microscope [1].

Chromogenic medium: Colony was streaked on HiCrome *Candida* Differential agar-a chromogenic media and incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours. Species of *Candida* were identified by color of colonies on media as per manufacturer's instructions [7] as follows:

Candida albicans: light green colored smooth colonies.

Candida tropicalis: blue to metallic blue coloured raised colonies.

Candida glabrata: cream to white smooth colonies.

Candida krusei: purple fuzzy colonies.

Candida parapsilosis: light pink colonies

Candida guilliermondii: light pink colonies

Corn meal agar: Using Dalmau's method of inoculation, colonies were inoculated into Corn meal agar with Tween 80, covered with a coverslip, incubated at 25°C for 72 hours in dark and examined by placing the plate without lid under low power and high power objectives of microscope for presence of blastoconidia, pseudohyphae or chlamydospore at edge of coverslip [8].

Sugar fermentation: For each isolate, 4 test tubes containing sterile sugar fermentation media with Durham's tube and 2% concentration of the 4 sugars (glucose, maltose, sucrose and lactose) were inoculated with colonies of *Candida* and incubated at 30°C or 37°C for 2-10 days. The ability to ferment a sugar was shown by presence of acid (Andrade's indicator turning pink) and gas trapped in inverted Durham's tube. The different species of *Candida* were identified as follows [9].

Table 1:

Species	Dextrose	Sucrose	Maltose	Lactose
<i>C.albicans</i>	AG	-	AG	-
<i>C.tropicalis</i>	AG	AG	AG	-
<i>C.krusei</i>	AG	-	-	-
<i>C.parapsilosis</i>	AG	-	-	-
<i>C.guilliermondii</i>	AG	AG	-	
<i>C.glabrata</i>	AG	-	-	-

Sugar assimilation: commercially available sugar discs (dextrose, sucrose, maltose, lactose, galactose,

trehalose, cellobiose, melibiose, raffinose and dulcitol) were placed on carbohydrate free yeast

nitrogen base agar plate, incubated at 30°C for 18-24 hours and examined for growth around individual sugar disc, indicating assimilation of that particular

carbohydrate and absence of growth was interpreted as no assimilation. Different species of *Candida* were identified accordingly [8].

Table 2:

	Dextrose	Maltose	Sucrose	Lactose	Galactose	Melibiose	Cellulose	Inositol	Xylose	Raffinose	Trehalose	Dulcitol
<i>C.albicans</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	-
<i>C.tropicalis</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-
<i>C.parapsilosis</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	-
<i>C.guilliermondii</i>	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
<i>C.glabrata</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
<i>C.krusei</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>C.lusitaniae</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-
<i>C.dubliniensis</i>	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Biofilm: Biofilm formation of all the *Candida* isolates were detected by three standard methods- Tissue culture plate method, Tube method and Congo red agar method described by Pragyana Panda et al (2016) [10] and Shilpa khatri et al (2015).

Tissue culture plate method was considered as gold standard method [11]. Biofilm production by each isolate was scored as negative, moderate positive, or strong positive.

1) Tissue culture plate method: Isolates were inoculated in brain heart infusion (BHI) broth with 2% sucrose, incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. The broth was diluted to a one in 100 ratio using fresh medium. 0.2 ml of the diluted cultures were added to each well of the 96 well flat bottom polystyrene plates and incubated at 37°C.

Following incubation, the wells' contents were cautiously removed, washed four times with 0.2 ml of phosphate buffer saline (pH 7.2), fixed with sodium acetate (2%) for thirty minutes and stained with crystal violet (0.1% w/v). After thoroughly cleaning the excess discoloration with deionized water, the plates were set aside to dry. Adherent cells were evenly stained with crystal violet and produced a coating on all of the side wells.

An ELISA auto reader was used to measure the optical densities (OD) of the stained adherent *Candida* at a wavelength of 570 nm (OD 570 nm) and were graded as strong positive, moderate positive and negative [10].

2) Tube method: Ten milliliters of BHI broth containing 2% sucrose, were mixed with a loopful of *Candida* from overnight culture plates and the mixture was then cultured for 24 hours at 37°C.

After being decanted, the tubes were cleaned with PBS (pH 7.3) and allowed to dry. After that, dried tubes were stained for 30 minutes with crystal violet (0.1%). After removing excess stain, the tubes were dried and checked for the development of biofilm. It was determined that biofilm growth was taking

place when a measurable coating covered the tube's bottom and wall [10].

3) Congo red agar method: BHI agar with 5% sucrose and Congo red solid medium was used. Isolate was inoculated into this plate, incubated for 24 to 48 hours at 37°C. Black colonies with a dry crystalline consistency showed a positive outcome [11].

Antifungal susceptibility test: The antifungal susceptibility testing was performed by modified disc diffusion method on Mueller Hinton agar (MHA) containing, 0.5µg/ml methylene blue and 2% dextrose with two drugs; fluconazole 25µg, and voriconazole 1µg discs according to CLSI guidelines, M44-A2 document [12].

The zone of inhibition was measured to the nearest whole millimeter and interpreted according to CLSI guidelines, M27M44S edition 3 document [13]. *C. albicans* ATCC 90028 was used as a quality control strain in identification as well as for antifungal susceptibility test.

Culture media was prepared in-house and antifungal discs were obtained from Himedia Laboratories, Bengaluru.

Results

A total of 40 clinically significant isolates of *Candida* species from various clinical samples of cancer patients were characterised. Twenty one of these isolates were from males (52.5%) and 19 isolates from females (47.5%).

Maximum number of samples belonged to the age group of 41-60 (15/40), followed by above 60 years (12), 0-20 years (8) and 21-40 years (5).

Among the 40 *Candida* isolates, 8 were from blood samples, 7 from urine samples, 6 from pus, 4 from sputum, 6 from throat swab, 1 from tracheal secretion, 4 from stool, 1 from vaginal swab and 3 from other body fluids. The clinical presentations of these patients included sepsis, urinary tract

infection, and diarrhoea, wound infection, oral thrush, cough with expectoration and pain abdomen. Among the 40 isolates, 21 isolates were from patients with haematological malignancies and 19

were from patients with solid organ tumours. Majority (25%) of the candida isolates were from patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia (Table 3).

Table 3:

Diagnosis	No. of isolates	Percentage (%)
Hematological malignancies		
AML	6	15%
ALL	10	25%
Multiple myeloma	3	7.5%
Solid tumour malignancies		
Carcinoma colon	4	1%
Carcinoma breast	3	7.5%
Carcinoma tonsil	3	7.5%
Carcinoma pancreas	2	5%
Carcinoma of buccal mucosa	3	7.5%
Lymphoma	2	5%
Carcinoma cervix	2	5%
Giant cell tumour	1	2.5%
Retinoblastoma	1	2.5%
Total	40	

Speciation by phenotypic methods: Out of the 40 Candida isolates, 67% of isolates were non albicans Candida as compared to 33% of Candida albicans. Amongst the non albicans Candida, Candida tropicalis was the most common candida species isolated. (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of various candida species:

Biofilm was detected in 77.5% isolates by tissue culture plate method, 60% isolates by both tube method and congo red agar method (Table 4).

Considering Tissue culture plate method as gold standard method, 31 (78%) of Candida species (C.albicans -8 (26%) and nonalbicans candida- 23 (74%) produced biofilm. Among the non albicans Candida, C. tropicalis (45%) was the most common biofilm producer. The distribution of candida species producing biofilm are as follows; C.

tropicalis 14 (45%), C. albicans 8 (25.8%), C. parapsilosis 4 (12.9%), C. glabrata and C. guilliermondii 2 (6.4%) each and C. lusitaniae 1 (3.2%), while none of the C. krusei isolates produced biofilm (Table 5).

ALL patients 10 (32%) were more associated with biofilm formation than patients with carcinoma cervix, pancreas, tonsil, lymphoma and giant cell tumour.

Table 4: Biofilm formation- comparison of 3 methods

Methods of biofilm detection	Biofilm Positive			Biofilm Negative
	Moderate positive	Strong positive	Total positives	
Tube method	19	5	24(60%)	16
Congo red agar method	20	4	24(60%)	16
Tissue culture plate method	22	9	31(77.5%)	9

Table 5: Biofilm production among various candida species:

Biofilm producing candida species	No. (%)
Candida albicans	8 (25.8%)
Candida tropicalis	14 (45%)
Candida parapsilosis	4 (2.9%)
Candida guilliermondii	2 (6.4%)
Candida glabrata	2 (6.4%)
Candida lusitaniae	1 (3.2%)
Candida krusei	0 (0%)
Total	31 (78%)

Antifungal susceptibility test showed, 70% of Candida isolates to be fluconazole sensitive and 30 % resistant (Figure 2), (Table 6). The sensitivity of C. albicans to fluconazole was 84.6% while that of

nonalbicans candida species were 62.9%. Voriconazole was found to be 92.5 % sensitive and 7.5% resistant (Figure 2) for all the studied isolates (Table 6).

Figure 2: Antifungal susceptibility testing by disk diffusion method showing fluconazole \leq 13mm and voriconazole \leq 14mm resistant.**Table 6: Antifungal susceptibility pattern of candida isolates:**

Species	Fluconazole (25 μ g)	Voriconazole (1 μ g)	Total
	R (%)	R (%)	
C. albicans	2(15.3%)	2(15.3%)	13
C. tropicalis	3(21.4 %)	0(0 %)	14
C. parapsilosis	2(40 %)	0(0%)	5
C. guilliermondii	0(0 %)	0(0 %)	2
C. glabrata	3(100%)	1(33.3%)	3
C. lusitaniae	0(0 %)	0(0 %)	1
C. krusei	2(100%)	0(0 %)	2
Total	12(30%)	3(7.5%)	40

Table 7: Correlation of biofilm producing Candida isolates with their antifungal resistance pattern:

Species	Biofilm producer		Total No. of biofilm producing candida spp (%)
	Fluconazole resistant No. (%)	Voriconazole resistant No. (%)	
<i>C. albicans</i>	1 (12.5%)	1 (12.5 %)	8 (25.8%)
<i>C. tropicalis</i>	3 (21.4 %)	0	14 (45%)
<i>C. parapsilosis</i>	2 (50 %)	0	4 (2.9%)
<i>C. guilliermondii</i>	0	0	2 (6.4%)
<i>C. glabrata</i>	2 (100 %)	1 (50 %)	2 (6.4%)
<i>C. lusitaniae</i>	0	0	1 (3.2%)
<i>C. krusei</i>	0	0	0 (0%)
Total	12 (30%)	3 (7.5%)	31 (78%)

Discussion

Candidemia is often connected with predisposing factors such as previous use of antibiotics, urinary tract instrumentation, use of immunosuppressive medication, diabetes mellitus, female, extremes in age, and prolonged hospital stays [14]. In many locations across the world, non-albicans candida species are now the most common pathogen, displacing *C. albicans* [15]. The synthesis of phospholipase, acid proteinase, biofilm development, and other factors are the primary causes of virulence in *Candida* species. Once in contact, extracellular proteins and cell membranes are broken down by enzymes, which promote adhesion [16]. Biofilm is a highly diverse, multilayered, multicellular, three-dimensional, extracellular matrix enveloping the yeast cells and allowing the cells to communicate and carry out specialized tasks. The components of the biofilm produced by *Candida* species are hyphae cells and blastospores. Antimicrobials and host defense mechanisms are not able to penetrate biofilm [17]. *Candida* frequently sticks to biomedical equipment and develops into a robust biofilm that may survive high antifungal doses [18].

In the present study, based on the conventional phenotypic methods for characterization of candida species, non-albicans candida were more, compared to *Candida albicans*. *C. tropicalis* (35%) was the most common candida species isolated from cancer patients followed by *C. albicans* 32.5%, *C. parapsilosis* 12.5%, *C. glabrata* 7.5%, while *C. krusei* and *C. guilliermondii* 5% each and *C. lusitaniae* 2.5%. In concordance with our study, Chakrabarthy A. et al [19] and Ratna Shukla [20] et al also found in their studies, that the commonest species was *C. tropicalis* followed by *C. albicans*.

In this study, biofilm formation was seen in 31(78%) of *Candida* species (*C. albicans*- 8(26%) and nonalbicans candida-23(74%). In the study conducted by Mythrey et al, 14(53.84%) of the *Candida* isolates were found to produce biofilm. Biofilm production was found to occur more frequently among non albicans *Candida*-10 (62.5%) than *Candida albicans* 4(40.0%) [14]. In the study

conducted by Vinitha et al in which 73% of *Candida* species isolates obtained from the clinical isolates produced biofilm in non-cancerous patients [16]. Thirty percent *Candida* isolates were fluconazole resistant and 8% were voriconazole resistant by modified disc diffusion method in this study. In a study conducted by Edula AR, fluconazole resistance rate was 18.6% and voriconazole resistance rate was 5% [21]. *Candida* species differed in their susceptibility to antifungal agents. On comparison of susceptibility pattern of *C. albicans* and non-albicans *Candida* species, it was observed that *C. albicans* is more susceptible to both the antifungal agents tested. Maximum fluconazole resistance was shown by *C. krusei* (100%) and *C. glabrata* (100%) and maximum voriconazole resistance was shown by *C. glabrata* (33.3%) in the present study. Non- albicans *Candida* has shown an increased resistance to azoles. Similar findings were shown by Edula AR [21].

On comparing the antifungal susceptibility pattern and biofilm formation, it was observed that only 30% of fluconazole resistant and 7.5% voriconazole resistant candida species produced biofilm. Among biofilm producing *C. albicans*, only 12.5% were fluconazole and voriconazole resistant. 21.4% fluconazole resistant *C. tropicalis* produced biofilm. None of the voriconazole resistant *C. tropicalis* were biofilm producers. Among biofilm producing *C. parapsilosis*, 50% were fluconazole resistant and none were voriconazole resistant. Among biofilm producing *C. guilliermondii* and *C. lusitaniae*, no isolates showed resistance to both antifungals tested. In biofilm producing *C. glabrata* isolates, 100% were resistant to fluconazole and 50% resistant to voriconazole (Table 7). Resistance to fluconazole is of great concern as it is the most common azole used for the treatment of candidiasis.

Conclusion

Widespread use of immunosuppressants in cancer patients predispose them to candida infections. Out of 40 candida isolates tested, *C. albicans*, *C. tropicalis*, *C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis*, *C. krusei*, *C. lusitaniae* and *C. guilliermondii* were the species of *Candida* isolated. *C. tropicalis* was the most common

Candida species isolated. It was observed that 78% of the isolates produced biofilm, with *C. tropicalis* as the commonest biofilm producer. Antifungal susceptibility testing of *Candida* isolates will be helpful in guiding physicians to select the appropriate antifungal drug so that therapeutic failures can be avoided thus decreasing patient morbidity and mortality. Considering high prevalence of non-albicans *Candida* species and species-specific intrinsic resistance to antifungals, it is important to speciate *Candida* isolates causing infections in cancer patients along with their biofilm formation and antifungal susceptibilities.

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References

- Chander J. Textbook of Medical Mycology. Fourth edition. Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers; 2018. 946 p.
- Abdel-Hamid RM, El-Mahallawy HA, Abdelfattah NE, Wassef MA. The impact of increasing non-albicans *Candida* trends on diagnostics in immunocompromised patients. *Braz J Microbiol Publ Braz Soc Microbiol*. 2023 Dec; 54(4):2879–92.
- Morace G, Sanguinetti M, Posteraro B, Lo Cascio G, Fadda G. Identification of various medically important *Candida* species in clinical specimens by PCR-restriction enzyme analysis. *J Clin Microbiol*. 1997 Mar; 35(3): 667–72.
- Bansal R, Tiwari YK, Patidar V. Biofilm Formation among Various *Candida* Species and its Role in Antifungal Resistance at Tertiary Care Centre, Jhalawar. *Int J Contemp Med Res IJCMR* [Internet]. 2019 May [cited 2024 Sep 10]; 6(5). Available from: https://www.ijcmr.com/uploads/7/7/4/6/77464738/ijcmr_2493.pdf
- Prakash V, Verma D, Agarwal S. Candiduria: its characterization, antifungal susceptibility pattern and biofilm formation. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2018 Nov 26; 6(12):4070–6.
- Koneman EW, Allen SD, Janda WM, Schreckenberger PC, Winn WC. Color Atlas and Textbook of Diagnostic Microbiology. 5th edition. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 1997. 1488 p.
- Mehta R, Wyawahare AS. Evaluation of Hicrome *Candida* Differential Agar for Species Identification of *Candida* Isolates from Various Clinical Samples. 2016; 3(4).
- Walsh TJ, Hayden RT, Larone DH. Larone's Medically Important Fungi: A Guide to Identification. 6th edition. Washington, District of Columbia: ASM Press; 2018. 550 p.
- Parija SC, House AP. Practical Microbiology For Under Graduate Medical Students. 2018th edition. Ahuja Publishing House; 2018. 119 p.
- Panda PS, Chaudhary U, Dube SK. Comparison of four different methods for detection of biofilm formation by uropathogens. *Indian J Pathol Microbiol*. 2016; 59(2):177–9.
- Khatri S, M N S, Mahale R, Kishore A. Analysing three different screening methods for biofilm formation in clinical isolates of *Candida*. *J Evol Med Dent Sci*. 2015 Oct 14; 4:14515–24.
- Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. 2009. Method for antifungal disk diffusion susceptibility testing of yeasts; approved guideline, 2nd ed., M44-A2 Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute, Wayne, PA.
- Clinical & Laboratory Standards Institute [Internet]. [Cited 2024 Sep 9]. M27 M44S Ed3 | Performance Standards for Antifungal Susceptibility Testing of Yeasts, 3rd Edition. Available from: <https://clsi.org/standards/products/microbiology/documents/m27m44s/>
- Rishpana MS, Kabbin JS. Candiduria in Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection with Special Reference to Biofilm Production. *J Clin Diagn Res JCDR*. 2015 Oct; 9(10):DC11–3.
- R Y, M P S, U A B, R R, K B A. Candiduria: prevalence and trends in antifungal susceptibility in a tertiary care hospital of mangalore. *J Clin Diagn Res JCDR*. 2013 Nov; 7(11):2459–61.
- Mohandas V, Ballal M. Distribution of *Candida* Species in Different Clinical Samples and Their Virulence: Biofilm Formation, Proteinase and Phospholipase Production: A Study on Hospitalized Patients in Southern India. *J Glob Infect Dis*. 2011; 3(1):4–8.
- Czechowicz P, Nowicka J, Gościński G. Virulence Factors of *Candida* spp. and Host Immune Response Important in the Pathogenesis of Vulvovaginal Candidiasis. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2022 May 24; 23(11):5895.
- Silva S, Rodrigues CF, Araújo D, Rodrigues ME, Henriques M. *Candida* Species Biofilms' Antifungal Resistance. *J Fungi*. 2017 Feb 21; 3(1):8.
- Chakrabarti A, Reddy TC, Singhi S. Does candiduria predict candidaemia? *Indian J Med Res*. 1997 Dec; 106:513–6.
- R S, Sg R, Ak B. A study of *Candida albicans* and non-albicans *Candida* species isolated from various clinical samples and their antifungal susceptibility pattern. *J Med Sci Res*. 2020 Jan 2; 8(1):1–11.
- Edula AR. Antifungal susceptibility of clinically significant *Candida* species by disk diffusion method. *IP Int J Med Microbiol Trop Dis*. 7(2):77–80.